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Investigating circularity in the construction and demolition sector through remote sensing: A case study of Bolzano/Bozen, Italy

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ABSTRACT

The built environment in urban areas contributes significantly to global waste generation through construction and demolition activities, highlighting the need for circular economy strategies to ensure sustainable development. Digital technologies offer fast and reliable methods to track material flows and improve resource efficiency. This study proposes a novel approach that integrates data from OpenStreetMap (OSM) and the Urban Atlas for land-use identification. The material stock (MS) is estimated via a geographic information system (GIS) to analyse the spatial characteristics of buildings, combined with material intensity (MI) data to assess the mass of materials within structures. Together with the quantification of material stock, hotspots of construction materials within the building stock are identified. When applied to the case study of Bolzano/Bozen, Italy, this approach estimated 130 tonnes per capita of accumulated building stock in the city and 40 tonnes per capita of material stock in infrastructure networks. This remote sensing methodology provides detailed insights into the quantity and distribution of materials in buildings and networks. The openness and availability of OSM data, as well as their independence from cadastral records, make this approach particularly advantageous for obtaining input data for the life cycle assessment (LCA) of buildings and the development of waste management strategies.

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1. Introduction

The concept of circular economy (CE) opposes traditional resource consumption, as it suggests keeping materials and goods circulating within the economy, designing products for longevity, and utilizing the residues as a resource for new products (Li & Xu, 2022; Yang et al., 2023). Modern technology can greatly assist in enhancing resource management and supporting policymakers in the implementation of CE strategies (Chen et al., 2024; Danish and Senjyu, 2023a,b; Khajuria et al., 2022). Cities are the first in line for implementing CE practices, as highly concentrated infrastructures, industries and dense populations require considerable energy and resources to function and generate a vast amount of waste (Calisto Friant et al., 2023; He et al., 2023; Qi et al., 2024). Cities contain large amounts of natural resources stored in buildings, infrastructures, products, and waste deposits (Angelopoulos et al., 2019; Valera et al., 2023).

Within cities, construction and demolition are key economic sectors with substantial environmental impacts, contributing 37% of global energy-related GHG (greenhouse gas) emissions, and are responsible for excessive resource use and pollution (Al Sholi et al., 2023; UNEP, 2021). Circularity in construction aims to focus on durable materials, design for disassembly, and recovery schemes (Ng & Chau, 2015; Stephan & Athanassiadis, 2018; Wiedenhofer et al., 2015; Xu et al., 2024), as well as improving material documentation and traceability (Højbye & Sand, 2018; Minunno et al., 2018). The incorporation of recycled materials reduces resource demand and contamination risks while enabling by-product reuse in new concrete production (Minunno et al., 2018; Purchase et al., 2021).

Urban mining could provide independence for natural resource extraction by repurposing or recycling urban infrastructure and materials that are no longer in use for new applications (Cossu & Williams, 2015; Iacovidou & Purnell, 2016). Reusing construction materials can lead to significant resource savings, reduce landfill waste, and lower the energy needed to produce new materials (Zeng et al., 2022). Urban mining research faces challenges, as data

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on new construction projects are typically well documented, whereas information on renovation and demolition activities is often unavailable and not precise (Aldebei & Dombi, 2021). Inaccuracies in the locations of buildings and their morphologies complicate the estimation of resource quantity (Koutamanis et al., 2018; Rajaratnam et al., 2023).

Geographic information system (GIS) is widely used in building stock (BS) analysis. For example, Meinel et al. (2009) presented a GIS-based approach that integrates topographic and digital maps with municipal data to generate structure parameters, such as building density, age, and configuration, enabling cost-effective, nationwide tracking of BS changes over different time periods and offering insights into the temporal changes within the built environment. In a city-level study conducted for Vienna, Kleemann et al. (2017) demonstrated a way to analyse material stock (MS) in buildings and their spatial distribution, combining GIS data on the building material composition and structure sources from different municipal authorities to generate specific material intensities (MIs) for various building categories, distinguished by utilization and period of construction. Cheng et al. (2018) analysed building statistical data for Taipei city and performed hot-spot analysis to identify areas most suitable for urban ore extraction with GIS. García-Pérez et al. (2018) showed how spatial analysis with GIS facilitates life cycle assessment (LCA) inventories, providing information about critical areas within a city and visualizing clear results for stakeholders. Da Paz et al. (2018) employed GIS to plan a network for CDW (construction and demolition waste) management in Recife, Brazil, confirming the importance of spatial analysis to locate CDW properly and improve the recyclability of materials. Wu et al. (2016) developed a GIS-based model to quantify and predict waste from demolition activities, from the generation stage to its final disposal, providing a visual representation of the CDW location.

The studies above demonstrate how GIS facilitate data processing and management to perform building stock analysis and further use software for circular economy applications. However, the building information was obtained mainly from governmental or municipal sources, in some cases including analyses of historical maps of cities. To avoid cadastral records, machine learning methods can be applied to derive data from satellite images. The steel stock in Japan, China, Republic of Korea etc. was estimated by Hsu et al. (2011) via a method based on nighttime light (NTL) satellite images in combination with land cover data. In this way, remote sensing (RS) has allowed the analysis of steel stocks in various regions and countries where it has not been reported before. Later, the method was applied to the global scope, concluding that the NTL was correlated with the steel stocks, depending on the specifics of a region (Hsu and Matsuno, 2013). Vilaysouk et al. (2021) acquired data on total in-use stock via a dynamic MS model, with a correlation coefficient of 0.94, confirming the usefulness of NTL in MS assessment in the case of conventional data unavailability. However, the drawback of the NTL approach for MS evaluation is the misinterpretation of the luminosity and miscibility of nonluminous structures (Haberl et al., 2021). Mapping MS at the country level for Germany and Austria, Haberl et al. (2021) suggest extracting data on the physical features of infrastructures from combined sources, which are open and available data from OpenStreetMap (OSM) and satellite images, avoiding cadasters; however, MI data are still needed to calculate the mass of materials for mapping (Cheng et al., 2018; Gontia et al., 2018).

Despite advances in GIS for BS estimation, there remains a lack of accurate cadastral data on infrastructures, which makes it challenging and protracted to source and analyse building information. With respect to alternatively deriving data from satellite

images, training the ML model with enough samples can be time-consuming for a small area of interest and provide results with errors greater than those obtained from GIS-based sources. This study presents an approach that enables rapid, remote-sensing-based estimation of MS in buildings and networks for small- and medium-sized cities. As an accessible and scalable substitute for traditional cadastral data, the method suggests OpenStreetMap (OSM) as a source for infrastructure footprints, together with digital surface models (DSMs) for building heights and the Urban Atlas for land use. Combining these sources with material intensity (MI) data enhances the feasibility of localized MS assessments and allows the calculation of urban MS with sufficient spatial resolution and accuracy.

Bolzano/Bozen, a small-to-medium-sized city in northern Italy with a population of approximately 107,000, represents a compelling case study for geospatial MS evaluation. With the building stock reflecting both Austrian-style architecture in the historic center and modern Italian constructions in newer districts, the city, being in between, benefits from existing studies on building stocks in both Italy and Austria, enabling the application of existing material intensity data, as well as comparison of the results. Furthermore, active municipal strategies for the sustainable construction sector in Bolzano/Bozen underscore the need for a detailed assessment of the building stock, making the city a solid context in which to test and refine remote-sensing MS localization approaches. Therefore, the following research questions are addressed: (1) How can remote sensing technologies facilitate the assessment of material stocks in the construction sector? (2) How much material stock is embedded in the infrastructures of Bolzano/Bozen? (3) How are the construction materials distributed within a city, and how can material stock mapping contribute to resource management at the city scale?

2. Data and methodology

In this study, the analysed infrastructure stocks involved in the construction sector include building stocks and those accumulated on roads and railways. With the OSM being a dynamic data source for infrastructure morphology, the presented method stands out for its ability to calculate and map the MS currently presented within the study area, and it provides a possibility to track changes in MS over time.

2.1. GIS-based methods and calculations

The bottom-up approach involves the calculation of MS from physical attributes of infrastructures, i.e., dimensions of buildings and roads, and coefficients, which characterize building and road material composition. In this way, two datasets are collated and combined: (1) the material intensity coefficient (MIC) dataset with information on material composition and (2) the GIS dataset with the geospatial characteristics of infrastructures.

Having obtained the physical features of buildings in the form of volume V [m^3] and their material composition as MIC [kg/m^3], the following equation allows the calculation of the MS per building (Kleemann et al., 2017):

$$M_{m,k} = \left(V_k * MIC_{m,i,j} \right)$$

where $M_{m,k}$ is the mass of material m contained in building k belonging to building category i, j ; V_k is a building's volume; $MIC_{m,i,j}$ is a specific material intensity coefficient of material m for building category i, j ; and each building category is characterized by i -land-use, j -construction period.

The mass of a particular material can be found by summing the obtained masses of materials in single buildings:

$$M_m = \sum_{k=1}^n M_{m,k}$$

By summing the masses of each material, the total material stock [kg] can be determined. The obtained masses of MS would allow the spatial distribution of materials within the study area to be created for further evaluation. Fig. 1 summarizes the workflow for data collection and processing, with further detailed descriptions in Sections 2.2 and 2.3.

Starting data gathering from the material intensity coefficients (MICs) is suggested. The level of detail in the MIC dataset directly influences the amount of data needed, indicating the need for supplementary data in building characterization. The accuracy of how the resulting material composition is estimated also depends on how the MICs are compiled, with higher detail reducing potential bias. In this study, pre-compiled MIC datasets organized by building type and construction period were utilized. Consequently, to accurately assign building volumes to MICs for MS calculations, each building must be categorized according to the corresponding type and construction period defined in the MIC dataset. Similarly, infrastructure networks are classified based on the specific MIC dataset employed.

2.2. Building categories and material intensity dataset

The material intensity can be defined as the average content of material per unit area or volume of a building. A specific MIC represents the amount of a particular material typically present in buildings, expressed per unit of volume, floor area, or a comparable metric. MIC values are categorized according to building type, land use, and construction period. These coefficients serve as standardized metrics that connect building parameters with material composition and facilitate the estimation of MS in urban environments. The data can be extracted from various sources,

including construction reports, cadastral databases, or previous investigations conducted in the region of interest.

The categorization of buildings depends on the available data on construction activities in the studied region and the precision of the material composition information for buildings and networks. Since none of the studies were conducted on building material evaluation in South Tyrol, the MIC databases compiled for German, Austrian and Italian cities were analysed in terms of the historical background and geographical location of the studied region. Considering that the main construction activity took place after World War II, when Italian construction standards and regulations were already applied, the closest MIC dataset for buildings in Bolzano/Bozen resulted from the Padua case study (Miatto et al., 2019). The investigation included national reports and manuals minimizing sourcing data from international studies to calculate the MIC for Italian buildings, making the resulting database applicable for remote-sensing-based analysis within Italian regions.

Residential buildings are the most common in South Tyrol with respect to the built area (Filippi Oberegger et al., 2020). Given the absence of ready-to-use data on industrial and other special purpose buildings (e.g., hospitals, churches), these buildings were excluded from the MS analysis. Therefore, for the case study of Bolzano/Bozen, buildings were categorized in three categories: (1) small residential (single-family houses, height up to 6 m), (2) medium (multi-family houses, height up to 12 m), and (3) large (apartment blocks, height over 12 m). The fourth category is non-residential buildings, which include shops and other commercial offices. The floor height was taken as an average value of 2.7 m.

The MIC dataset for buildings used in this study was compiled based on materials employed in Italian construction, as described by Miatto et al. (2019). This dataset provides MIC values for 13 materials across 24 building categories, which are classified by four types of land use—small residential, medium residential, large residential, and non-residential—and are differentiated by six construction periods, presented as cohorts: until 1902, 1903–1954, 1955–1969, 1970–1981, 1982–1996, and 1997–2007.

Fig. 1. Workflow for data collection and evaluation.

Materials include mortar, lightweight concrete, concrete, steel, bricks, timber, glass, synthetic insulation, mineral insulation, other insulation materials, bituminous waterproofing, flooring materials, and other materials.

The construction period data for buildings in Bolzano/Bozen were sourced from ISTAT (Italian National Institute of Statistics) and compared with the original MIC dataset to identify mismatches in time intervals. To join the datasets, a new set of construction periods was established, which is consistent with local records: before 1918, 1919–1945; 1946–1960, 1961–1970, 1971–1980, 1981–1990, 1991–2000, 2001–2005, and 2006; and after. To estimate MIC values for these new periods, it was assumed that the variation in material composition across cohorts in the original data had a linear trend. Similarly, in the Padua dataset, the following cohorts were established for Bolzano/Bozen's MIC calculation: 1918, 1945, 1960, 1970, 1980, 1990, 2000, and 2005. A linear regression model was implemented in Python. For each typology, the original MIC values y were regressed against their corresponding construction cohort x via Python's `LinearRegression()` from the `sklearn.linear_model` module, and material coefficients for Bolzano/Bozen were derived from the model. The regression coefficients and obtained dataset of the MICs can be found in the which is in the Electronic Supplementary Material (ESM) in the online version of this paper. The values obtained for the construction cohorts were then assigned to periods.

For networks, the MIC dataset compiled for Austria by Haberl et al. (2021) was utilized for Bolzano/Bozen, considering the close proximity of the study area to Austria. The values are provided for 3 types of networks, namely, main roads, general roads and railways, with the following materials in composition: metals, concrete, road aggregate, and petrochemical-based materials. The city center of Bolzano/Bozen is considered to be covered with cobble stones; thus, the dataset was complemented with a fourth category consisting of porphyry material. The MIC for the porphyry material was calculated based on construction records obtained from municipal records.

2.3. Data inventory for the GIS dataset

In this study, the geospatial data were processed in QGIS software v. 3.34.13. To complete the geospatial dataset for multiplication with the MIC, each building must be assigned a volume value. Depending on how detailed the MIC dataset is and what building categories it includes, each building must also be assigned a category; to do so, in the case of Bolzano/Bozen, information on its land use and construction period is needed.

The data on building and road footprints for the area of interest can be downloaded via the "OpenStreetMap" plug-in in QGIS in the form of a layer with mapped polygons, which does not require additional manual processing. Another option for obtaining information on building footprint areas is to download data from local geoportals. In this way, the data would be proven by official sources; however, they may not be available for some regions.

To evaluate the building height, a digital surface model (DSM) was downloaded from the Autonomous Province of Bolzano/Bozen

geoportal. In the QGIS, the downloaded raster layer contains values with the elevation of a particular point. When a polygon is joined with a building layer, it provides the height of a chosen polygon; within a polygon, there are points with various height values, and the average is calculated and assigned as the height of a polygon. As each polygon represents a building, with area and height values assigned, it is possible to calculate a building volume for further MS evaluation.

The land-use data were sourced from the Urban Atlas and imported into QGIS, resulting in a layer with residential and industrial areas. The usability of the Urban Atlas is based on the availability of information and its open access for every major European city. Land-use data can also be obtained from local geoportals and from the OSM; however, these data can be complex, and further processing may be needed. Combining an already compiled map of buildings in Bolzano/Bozen with a land-use layer would reveal the characteristics of a building's utilization, which is based on the area where a polygon falls on a land-use map. In addition, specific points were determined when a residential building would have the ground floor occupied with commercial use, such as shops, private clinics, etc. Information on specific use regarding this type of location was sourced from the OSM. For the Bolzano/Bozen case study, the construction period data sourced from ISTAT were not available for each single building but rather for a census area with an indication of how many buildings were built in a certain period. Thus, the construction periods within the district were randomly assigned to single buildings within the QGIS.

A similar approach was applied to estimate MS in networks. The networks were classified into four categories: railways, main roads (motorways), general roads, and cobblestone pavements in the city center. As the MICs were obtained in units of kg/m^2 , data on the road area were required for further calculation. Data on area and land use information were sourced from the OSM.

2.4. Limitations of the methodology and data validation

The methodology used in this study presents several limitations, primarily related to the availability and quality of the input data and the assumptions inherent to the modeling approach. These factors introduce uncertainty at various stages of the workflow and influence the reliability of the final MS estimates, as summarized in Table 1.

The first significant limitation of coefficient-based methods is their reliance on generalized MICs. These values are calculated as averages for a building category, overlooking unique construction practices, failing to account for local construction methods and specifics and introducing uncertainty in the quantification of stocks. However, Miatto et al. (2019) reported that they derived MICs from Italian construction norms, manuals, and field surveys; this approach minimally addresses international studies and is tailored specifically for Italian cities, making their dataset as precise as possible. As mentioned in Section 2.2, the city of Bolzano/Bozen is believed to have a strong Italian influence on construction. Therefore, using Italian MICs would likely yield the most accurate results for evaluating material stocks in this region.

Table 1
Parameters for MS calculation.

Input parameter	Source	Precision or resolution
MICs	Literature	Averages based on historic manuals; liner regression R^2 score mostly over 0.85
Building and road footprints	OSM	OSM positional accuracy of 1.57 m; crowd-sourced and may result in inaccurate polygon boundaries
Building heights	DSM from local geoportal	DSM resolution of 2.5 m
Construction period	ISTAT	Census-based; random assignment within a district with moderate uncertainty
Land-use	Urban Atlas	Spatial accuracy ± 5 m; thematic accuracy at least 85%

The more building categories the MIC dataset includes, the more accurate the composition of infrastructure that can be obtained. Although not mandatory, including data on construction periods and land use significantly improves the accuracy of quantification. With respect to building typology, differentiation within residential buildings was performed on the basis of a building height calculated according to the DSM with 2.5 m resolution; non-residential buildings were identified via Urban Atlas data, as were some specific use buildings marked on the OSM. The Urban Atlas typically has spatial accuracy within 5 m, and the thematic accuracy for urban classes is at least 85%.

However, adjusting primary data to be compatible via statistical methods decreases its reliability. Evaluating the reliability of the linear regression developed for estimating MICs, the coefficient of determination (R^2) exceeded 0.85 for critical materials across nearly all building categories, with root mean square error (RMSE) values being consistently within 20%, taken as an acceptable degree of model fit with a relatively low average prediction error. Comparatively lower R^2 values were observed for materials such as glass, lightweight concrete and insulation materials. This outcome is due primarily to the relatively low quantities of these materials used per building in the initial dataset and the reduced precision of the historical data. Additionally, their MICs differ by two to three orders of magnitude from those of more dominant materials such as brick or reinforced concrete, so given their minor contribution to the overall material mass, the impact of this variation on total material demand estimations could be considered negligible.

Since the construction period data were aggregated at the district level, resulting in a random assignment of periods to buildings within each district, a Monte Carlo simulation was performed to evaluate the uncertainty of such an approach. With 1000 simulations, average assignment entropy across all census areas was analysed to determine how much the average uncertainty in building age assignments differed from one census area to another. There are a notable number of areas with very low entropy close to 0, indicating areas where building ages are highly

certain; the average entropy across all 279 census areas being approximately 1.55 bits suggests that many areas have a moderate level of uncertainty in their building age assignments. An incorrect assignment of a construction period to a building results in mis-arranged MICs and, consequently, in exact building-level material masses; nonetheless, its overall effect on total material stock estimates across census areas remains generally limited. With that, random allocation minimizes systematic errors and does not involve unverified assumptions.

The accuracy of the GIS dataset is strongly related to the precision and limitations of the OSM, which is a main data source. OSM includes a combination of satellite imagery and crowd-sourced data, thus offering a more comprehensive representation of BSs and infrastructure rather than statistical sources. High-resolution satellite images typically have spatial resolutions of 0.3–1 m and can identify and map infrastructures in considerable detail. The positional accuracy of OpenStreetMap was tested by El-Ashmawy (2016), who reported a positional accuracy of 1.57 m. Despite the high accuracy of OSM data for network areas, the uncertainty in road and rail material estimates exceeds that of OpenStreetMap due to insufficient region- and time-specific material intensities and limited data on infrastructure age and poor data quality, especially for communal and provincial roads, which dominate the networks (Wiedenhofer et al., 2015).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Material stocks and heatmaps

By combining the geospatial dataset of buildings and networks for Bolzano/Bozen with the MIC dataset, the mass of construction materials for each building was calculated via GIS software. The charts in Fig. 2 illustrate the material stocks of buildings found in the city of Bolzano/Bozen according to the cohort and building typology. The distribution by building type shows that large residential buildings consistently contain the highest total material stocks, followed by non-residential buildings, with medium and

Fig. 2. Building material stocks in the city of Bolzano/Bozen, 10^6 kg.

small residential buildings containing significantly less material. This pattern holds true across all time periods but is most visible in earlier decades, suggesting that larger buildings not only use more material but also have a more diverse material palette as construction methods evolve. Overall, a temporal transition is traced from brick-dominated construction to a more balanced use of brick and concrete, especially in larger and non-residential buildings, reflecting broader trends in urban development and material innovation. The presence of mortar remains relatively stable, whereas timber and other materials contribute only minor fractions to the overall material stock, with slight increases in the most recent construction periods, possibly reflecting more diverse or hybrid construction approaches. Overall, brick, concrete and timber make up more than 90% of the material stock in Bolzano/Bozen. Table 2 presents the results of the material stock of infrastructures calculated for the city of Bolzano, with Table 3 summarizing the material content of buildings divided by category. The materials are not evenly distributed among building types, with non-residential buildings constituting 25% of the BS. Large residential buildings naturally contain the largest volume of materials, with half of the building materials stored in this type of infrastructure.

The composition of the roads is dominated by aggregates, with much smaller contributions from porphyry, concrete, and metals, yielding 4.37 Mt of stocks overall, with the road aggregates accounting for 98% of the material stocks. The utilized MIC allows the calculation of the metal content in networks; however, the exact composition remains unknown, limiting further application of the obtained results.

Furthermore, the distributions of the chosen building materials were visualized in the form of heatmaps, as presented in Fig. 3. Fig. 4 presents the network division within the city, distinguishing key network types. Notably, the city center and the northern part of Bolzano/Bozen, which are residential areas, have a high

accumulation of bricks. Their dominant presence reflects the use of traditional construction materials in historical buildings, as they often have thick walls and are densely built, which increases the material mass per square meter. Minimal usage of concrete in the center can be noted, and traditional methods of construction also do not include insulation; therefore, insulation materials are essentially absent in the central area.

The southern part of Bolzano/Bozen is characterized by industrial buildings, where concrete is the dominant construction material, as represented on the heatmap in Fig. 3(a). The notable accumulation of bricks observed on the map may be due to methodological factors, as industrial buildings typically have large volumes. Furthermore, in areas with extensive use of traditional concrete, lightweight concrete is also incorporated, possibly indicating an effort to adopt more sustainable construction practices. Steel is largely contained in the industrial area of Bolzano/Bozen, whereas residential areas are the primary structural material in factories, comprising frames, roofs, and reinforcements. The combination of material types in the industrial area highlights its potential as a resource hub for material recovery and recycling, particularly for high-value materials.

The distribution of insulation materials in Bolzano/Bozen shows distinct patterns influenced by urban zoning and building typologies. Residential areas outside the center consist of newer residential developments where modern construction practices prioritize energy efficiency, leading to widespread use of insulating materials. For the city center, the heatmap indicates the absence of insulation in buildings, reflecting the challenges of retrofitting historical buildings with modern insulation systems. Notably, Fig. 3(c) represents the potential mass quantity of the insulation material but does not reflect the energy efficiency of buildings.

3.2. Applications of the method for the circular economy

The spatial material stock map developed in this study provides a foundation for advancing CE strategies in the construction and demolition sectors, with practical applications for material recovery, environmental assessment, urban planning, and climate adaptation.

The industrial southern zone of Bolzano/Bozen, characterized by its abundance of steel and concrete, presents a significant opportunity for circular recovery during demolition or renovation. Considering that the recovery rate of CDW in the European Union is 89% (Caro et al., 2024), the area contains more than 200 Mt of steel material that can possibly be used instead of producing new steel from raw materials. Maps of insulation materials provide a clear understanding of where they are lacking, particularly in the city center, where buildings initially have minimal or no insulation. These insights can guide the municipality in implementing retrofitting programs aimed at improving energy efficiency, with mass-based data serving as foundational inputs for LCA and energy modelling. Even though for a small city such as Bolzano/Bozen, with an area of 52.3 km², spatial LCA might not be significant, such an approach may be combined with the LCA methodology for broader areas where distances might be more influential.

Table 2
Material stocks for buildings and networks in Bolzano/Bozen, 10⁶ kg.

	Material	Total mass, 10 ⁶ (kg)	Total (%)	
Material stock in buildings	Bricks	6891.7	49.53	
	Mortar	3068.6	22.06	
	Concrete	2830.4	20.34	
	Timber	488.2	3.51	
	Flooring	311.8	2.24	
	Steel	229.7	1.65	
	LW concrete	92.6	0.67	
	Glass	14.6	0.11	
	Bituminous waterproofing	4.1	0.03	
	Synthetic insulation	0.9	0.01	
	Mineral insulation	0.5	0.003	
	Other insulation	1.1	0.01	
	Other materials	34.0	0.02	
	All building materials	13912.8	100	
	Material stock in networks	Metals	8.38	0.19
		Concrete	14.46	0.33
		Road aggregate	4286.56	98.08
Petrochemical-based materials		47.76	1.09	
Porphyry		13.46	0.31	
All networks' materials		4370.62	100	

Table 3
Building stocks in buildings per typology, 10⁶ kg.

Mass	Small residential	Medium residential	Large residential	Non-residential	Total
In 10 ⁶ (kg)	772	2264	7329	3606	13,970.49
Per capita (kg)	7.21	21.16	68.50	33.70	130.57
Total (%)	5.52	16.20	52.46	25.81	100

Fig. 3. Visualization of the distribution of construction materials within the municipality of Bolzano/Bozen: (a) brick heatmap, (b) concrete heatmap, (c) insulation materials heatmap; and (d) network infrastructure in Bolzano/Bozen with asphalt roads (red), railway (purple), and cobblestone streets in the historic center (green).

The material maps also present new opportunities for urban planning and climate adaptation. By analysing the geographic distribution of thermally massive materials such as concrete and

brick and where insulation is imbedded, urban planners can assess urban heat island vulnerability. For example, areas with dense brick construction and limited insulation, such as historical

Fig. 4. Building stocks per capita of population: comparison with other studies (t/cap).

centers, may be more prone to heat accumulation during extreme weather events. Overlaying these material maps with climate or demographic data could support heatwave risk assessments, helping prioritize interventions such as green roofs or shading strategies.

3.3. Comparison with other studies

Owing to the lack of static data on the material composition of buildings in Bolzano/Bozen, the validity of the quantified stocks was assessed through comparisons with similar studies (Fig. 4). Given Bolzano/Bozen's geographical proximity to Austria and Germany, the per capita results were compared with those from BS studies conducted in these neighboring countries via various methodologies. Assuming a population of approximately 107,000 for Bolzano/Bozen in 2024, the total material stock was calculated to be 130 tonnes per capita.

Miatto et al. (2019) suggested that the BS for a city in a Western country does not differ significantly and can be expected to be 200 tonnes per person. Overall, the results of this study align with findings from BS analyses of other cities but present lower values than investigations conducted at the national scale for Germany and Austria (Haberl et al., 2021). The discrepancy in the results could be influenced by the type of land use in the study area. The inclusion of rural areas in country-level studies, where single-family houses, which typically contain higher material stocks per capita, are more prevalent. In contrast, urban areas tend to feature more apartment blocks, which have lower MS content per building and per capita.

The variation in MS between Bolzano/Bozen and Padua (Miatto et al., 2019) might be due to the relatively large industrial area in Bolzano/Bozen compared with the residential area. The MICs for non-residential buildings are generally lower than those for residential buildings. For example, small, medium and large residential buildings contain 20, 30, and 40 times more bricks, respectively, as can be seen in the table of building material intensities in the ESM; the mortar content is, on average, 10 times greater in residential buildings. Consequently, the industrial zone contributes less to the city's total material stock.

Methodological differences also influence the calculation of MICs themselves. One key variation across studies is the selection of building materials considered, as their mass can vary significantly across different building typologies. For example, in the cases of Germany and Austria, Haberl et al. (2021) distinguished concrete and bricks as the main construction materials while grouping other materials into broader categories, such as metals or bio-based materials. Additionally, the importance of differentiating construction periods in MS analysis is evident in MIC datasets, as the material intensity of key materials such as concrete and bricks has changed notably over time due to advancements in construction technologies. While most studies distinguish between four to five construction periods, some national-scale analyses compile datasets without accounting for the year of construction. Kleemann et al. (2017) analysed primarily older buildings to develop archetypes and compile MICs, which tend to result in higher material content per unit of volume. Compared with the results of Kleemann et al. (2017), Lederer et al. (2021) reported a lower total material stock, which they attributed to the inclusion of a larger proportion of newer buildings in their analysis. In the case of Bolzano/Bozen, the majority of buildings were constructed after 1950 via modern construction methods and lighter materials, which contributed to a lower overall building stock. Additionally, Lederer et al. (2021) highlighted that methodological differences could lead to variations in MICs of up to 25%, further contributing to discrepancies in stock estimations.

Shiller et al. (2017) conducted a study of MS in Germany with both bottom-up and bottom-down approaches, expanding the scope beyond BS and including buildings (subdivided as domestic and non-domestic), infrastructure, building services and consumer goods, reporting higher value per capita. They reported that the results from the bottom-up method accounted for only 53% of the top-down value; however, some estimations made via the bottom-up approach, particularly for the inflow of steel and various plastics, were greater than the values determined via the top-down method. It was suggested that the quality of bottom-up data for these materials is superior to that of the top-down data, further emphasizing the impact of the chosen methodology on the final results.

The results for Bolzano/Bozen were compared with two studies from regions that are not geographically close. Tanikawa and Hashimoto (2009) quantified the material stock of buildings, roads, and railways for an urban area of 8 km² in Salford (Manchester, UK). Their findings indicate that the total material stock is lower than that of Bolzano/Bozen. This discrepancy may be attributed to several factors, including a small sample size, differences in construction methods between southern and northern Europe, and a higher population density in the urban area, which results in less material stock per capita. In Taipei city, the stock of construction materials was calculated to be 68 tonnes per capita, approximately half the amount found in Bolzano/Bozen. However, it is important to note that the authors indicated that only 50% of the data used in their analysis were valid (Cheng et al., 2018). Additionally, developing countries typically exhibit lower material density in their buildings.

When calculated on a per capita basis, the MS in networks for Bolzano/Bozen is estimated to be 40 tonnes per capita. This result could have been cross-referenced with the study performed on networks in Austria by Haberl et al. (2021); however, direct comparisons between country-scale and city-scale studies may be inappropriate owing to variations in network types. At the national level, the material stock per capita tends to be greater due to the greater prevalence of highways, whereas Bolzano/Bozen, as a small city, consists primarily of general roads, which contain lower material quantities.

4. Conclusions and future research

The methodology developed in this study involved the integration of GIS to estimate material stocks in Bolzano/Bozen. Material stocks were calculated via OSM footprints, DSM, and a ready-to-use MIC from previous studies. With the OSM, which is a dynamic source and can provide up-to-date spatial data, the method has the advantage of presenting the latest MS distribution.

This study introduces a method for estimating urban material stocks by integrating open-source spatial data with material coefficients. This approach provides an accessible means for provisional assessments, allowing us to gain an initial understanding of embedded material stocks in a study area without the need to examine municipal building plans. Applied to the case of Bolzano/Bozen, the method allowed the quantification of construction materials and visualization of the spatial distribution, with approximately 130 tonnes per capita in buildings and 40 tonnes per capita in networks. However, while the method is designed to be replicable and transferable, it is constrained by the availability and quality of MIC data, which are not uniformly developed across regions and countries. The reliability of the results is highly dependent on the level of detail of the MICs, especially for infrastructure such as roads, where aggregated datasets do not provide a full picture of material composition, thus calling into question the reasonability of material recovery from road aggregates.

Although cadaster data were not utilized, it was still necessary to employ statistical data on buildings to increase the accuracy and validity of the final results. This increased the complexity of the approach with additional types of data to evaluate.

Addressing the gap in the analysis of the composition of non-residential buildings, as well as improving the representation of informal or unregistered structures, which are often missing from open-source spatial datasets such as OSM, would increase the completeness and equity of material stock assessments. Nevertheless, as it is unfeasible to acquire precise information on each building for remote-sensing-based studies, with solid primary sources, the presented method provides a decent MS representation for the study area.

From an urban mining perspective, future work could involve linking the material stock data obtained with energy performance indicators, helping refine LCA results and informing strategies for building retrofits. After quantifying the material content in building structures, it would be beneficial to analyse construction techniques to assess the quality, level of impurities, and potential for material reuse, which can further enhance strategies for promoting circularity in the construction sector.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ksenia Shkirman: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Anna Stoppato:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Fabio Giussani:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Simon Pezzutto:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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